

Reproducibility Study: Safe Deployment for Counterfactual Learning to Rank with Exposure-Based Risk Minimization

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Reproducibility is critical for validating machine learning research, yet many studies lack clarity in their implementation. This work assesses the reproducibility of the paper 'Safe Deployment for Counterfactual Learning to Rank with Exposure-Based Risk Minimization' [Gupta et al. 2023], which introduces Counterfactual Risk Minimization (CRM) to enhance safety in Learning to Rank (LTR) models. Using the YAHOO, ISTEELLA, and MSLR30K datasets, we attempted to replicate the original findings but encountered significant challenges due to missing code, dataset inconsistencies, and computational constraints. The absence of the 2023 code forced reliance on a 2024 repository, which differed in model definitions and configurations. While we partially reproduced results for YAHOO, outcomes for MSLR30K deviated substantially, and ISTEELLA was too resource-intensive to test. Our findings, analyzed through the PRIMAD Model, highlight barriers such as unclear documentation, unverified dependencies, and platform limitations, emphasizing the need for more rigorous reproducibility practices in ranking model research.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Learning to rank**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Learning to Rank, Counterfactual Learning to Rank, Safety, Reproducibility

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1 Introduction

Learning to Rank (LTR) is the core component of any search engine, determining which search results appear first and which get buried. The goal of LTR is to ensure that the most relevant results are displayed based on a given query. Traditionally, ranking models learn from relevance judgments provided by human annotators, who manually label search results as relevant or not. However, this process is time-consuming and expensive. [Gupta et al. 2023]

An alternative approach is to use click data—tracking which links users click on—to infer relevance. However, click data is inherently biased due to position bias: users tend to click on results that are easiest to see rather than those that are truly relevant. To correct for this bias, Counterfactual Learning to Rank (CLTR) utilizes Inverse Propensity Scoring (IPS), which assigns greater weight to clicks that are less likely due to their position. Unfortunately, IPS can be unreliable due to high variance when data is sparse, making safe deployment a challenge. [Gupta et al. 2023]

To mitigate this risk, a novel method, Counterfactual Risk Minimization (CRM), is introduced. CRM operates similarly to an experienced driver guiding a self-driving car—it ensures that learning progresses smoothly without disrupting the user experience. This is achieved by penalizing

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ranking models that deviate too far from safe models while still allowing for gradual improvement. The method employs explore-based divergence to maintain a balance between learning and stability.[Gupta et al. 2023]

Paper results indicate that CRM achieves comparable performance to the logging policy but at a significantly faster rate than other methods. It converges efficiently to the optimal solution, balancing safety and efficiency. However, an initial burn-in period remains, as the logging policy still needs to be estimated from the data. [Gupta et al. 2023]

2 Experimental Setup of the Paper

The experimental setup follows a semi-synthetic approach, utilizing three large datasets: YAHOO, ISELLA, and MSLR30K. These datasets contain search queries, documents, and manually labeled relevance judgments. The logging policy is trained on a small fraction (3%) of the relevance judgments to simulate a real-world production system. This logging policy acts as a proxy for an actual search engine, generating simulated click data used to evaluate different CLTR methods. The setup ensures a controlled environment for testing algorithm performance under various conditions.

To assess performance, the study compares CRM against several baselines:

- Naive Approach: Uses raw click data without any bias correction.
- Represents the absolute best possible performance, trained on actual relevance judgments.
- Standard Action-Based IPS: Uses IPS for bias correction.
- Action-Based CRM: Accounts for unknown logging policies during training.

The experimental results are averaged over 10 independent runs evaluated on held-out test sets. Statistical significance is determined using a two-sided Student’s t-test. Methods with significantly lower performance values are marked when differences are significant, while those with no significant difference are also noted. Although the paper does not explicitly mention different random seeds, they were likely used given the multiple experimental runs. Furthermore, the inclusion of 80% confidence intervals suggests that variance has been accounted for when reporting results. [Gupta et al. 2023]

However, discrepancies exist between the paper and its corresponding GitHub repository. The repository appears to be linked to a 2024 paper [Gupta et al. 2024] rather than the 2023 study [Gupta et al. 2023] under discussion, featuring models labeled as IPS, Doubly-Robust, Safe Doubly-Robust, and PRPO. These differ from the models described in the 2023 paper, which include Logging, Skyline, Naive, Action IPS, Action CRM, Exp. IPS, and Exp. CRM. The differences in model names and the absence of key implementations, such as Skyline and Naive, make it unclear how to map methodologies between the studies. Although the authors suggest modifying beta parameters to align the 2024 models with the 2023 study, they provide no clear guidance, leaving outcomes unverifiable.

Since the repository does not include the 2023 code, we instead ran our reproducibility study for the available 2024 models. The following sections outline our approach and findings.

3 Our Approach

After downloading the datasets, we installed all the required dependencies. However, the authors included their entire environment in the repository, requiring us to manually determine which libraries were necessary for running the code. It would have been preferable if the authors had provided a streamlined list of required dependencies. Additionally, one of the main challenges was that the repository does not specify a Python version, making it difficult to ensure compatibility. After some trial and error, we determined that Python 3.9 was the most suitable version.

In order to run the code, we utilized Lightning AI, an alternative cloud-based environment, to facilitate the execution of the experiments. However, a particularly problematic dependency was PyTorch Lightning. The specified version could not be installed due to compatibility issues, so we had to install a more recent version of PyTorch (Version 1.9.0). This led to breaking changes in certain methods, requiring manual modifications to the source code, particularly in the `logging_policy.py` script (line 222).

Next, we modified the configuration file provided by the authors to specify our own data and results paths. However, the repository does not specify that the paths in `config.yaml` must be adjusted each time a different dataset or experiment is run, necessitating manual updates before execution. Additionally, we found that the script does not automatically generate the required directories for storing results. As a result, we had to manually create these folders before running the experiments.

We then attempted to execute the logging policy script but encountered an issue: the entire codebase was linked to the authors' Weights & Biases (wandb) account. To proceed, we had to create our own wandb account to properly log the experiments. Furthermore, if multiple experiments were conducted sequentially, the previous logging policy had to be manually reset to avoid conflicts with earlier results. This crucial step was not documented in the repository and was only discovered through trial and error. Additionally, the absence of predefined hyperparameters required us to generate them manually by executing scripts in the `utils` folder, adding unnecessary complexity to the setup process. Frustratingly, we later discovered that the authors had uploaded the missing parameters just five days before the exercise deadline—after we had already invested significant time troubleshooting and configuring them ourselves. An earlier update would have significantly streamlined our efforts and reduced unnecessary delays. Moreover, we discovered that certain crucial parts of the code had been commented out, forcing us to manually identify and reintegrate them. This issue significantly delayed our progress, as we spent considerable time debugging and modifying the code.

After completing the setup, we were finally able to run the models. We ran the models for a different number of sessions but, due to computational limitations, we were unable to conduct 10 runs per model as originally intended. Then we updated the command-line arguments by replacing the default values with those explicitly mentioned in the paper. This involved modifying parameters such as the risk setting (`risk`), noise level (`noise`), number of logging sessions (`num_sessions`), and dataset selection (`dataset`). Additionally, we modified the `config.yaml` file by manually updating the paths for dataset storage (`root_dir`) and prediction logs (`predict_dir`).

4 Results

The following sections will present our results for each Dataset.

4.1 YAHOO

In the repository, there was a link to the Yahoo dataset, and the website provided two datasets: one named C14 and the other C14B. The dataset used in the experiment was C14B. We need to obtain permission from the Yahoo [website](#) to download the dataset. While we could download the C14 dataset immediately, we were unable to download the C14B dataset. We emailed the website for access, but we did not receive a response.

The difference between the two datasets is that C14B is a larger, more detailed version of C14. It contains two datasets (large and small) with more features (up to 700), explicit train/validation/test splits, and five levels of relevance judgments. Unlike C14, which provides fewer details, C14B specifies query and URL counts and normalizes all feature values to the $[0,1]$ range.

Model	Sessions=400	Sessions=4000	Sessions=40000	Sessions=400000000
Logging Policy	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
DR	0.6547	0.6736	0.6740	0.6816
IPS	0.6510	0.6594	0.6588	0.6741
PRPO Risk	0.6365	0.6713	0.6638	0.6837
DR Risk	0.6519	0.6488	0.6631	0.6610

Table 1. nDCG@5 Scores for Different Models and Session Sizes

Since we could not obtain C14B, we decided to continue the experiment with C14 and modified the code accordingly. As expected, the results were different.

4.2 ISTEELLA

The ISTEELLA LETOR dataset is one of the largest public dataset for training LTR models. However this size caused quite a few problems with regard to the computational requirements during our experiments. Training the baseline logging policy took over 45GB of RAM alone. In the end this attempt failed because there were problems with numerical stability in ranking document groups during TOP-k ($K = 5$) sampling and computing their log-scores. The original paper used a Plackett-Luce Model (PL-Model) to calculate ranking scores of each sample. One of the authors of the paper worked on computational feasibility of these models so that they can be applied in a CLTR context [Oosterhuis 2021]. The idea of calculating a probability distribution over a sample in this way comes from an earlier earlier statistical work and showed how the gradients used in this computation could be calculated via the REINFORCE algorithm [Williams 1992] and the Gumbel Softmax-Trick [Gumbel 1954]. There are some problems with regards to numerical stability in the original code. When calculating the probability scores the documents that are not part of the sample are not correctly masked resulting in their scores contributing to the final rankings. There is also a problem with regards to the application of the Gumbel Noise to the underlying distribution where the noise is subtracted (we are ranking the top results not the bottom most results) while they should have been added as shown in other literature using the PL-Model for ranking documents. There was also a problem with regards to the calculations blowing up to +Inf and -Inf as the exponentiation steps were conducted in normal space instead of log space. Further work is needed to evaluate the correct implementation of the ranker. We were unable to completely validate the corrected ranker with this dataset as there were still some other issues that we were unable to remove from the sourcecode.

4.3 MSLR30K

The experimental results, shown in Table 2 and Figure 1, show the differences compared to the paper. In our experiments, the nDCG@5 scores were much lower, around 0.25 for all session sizes, while the original study reported scores closer to 0.6. Additionally, the original study’s plots show smooth and consistent trends, but our plots are unstable and erratic, suggesting there may be problems with the code or implementation. We also didn’t see any reliable trends like the ones reported in the original paper, making it hard to compare our results. Overall, our outcomes are difficult to interpret because they are so different from the authors’ findings.

Model	Sessions=400	Sessions=4000	Sessions=40000	Sessions=400000000
DR	0.252213	0.102136	0.244842	0.249062
IPS	0.232151	0.247833	0.248495	0.247161
PRPO Risk	0.238230	0.248019	0.242880	0.246550
DR Risk	0.101420	0.101620	0.198990	0.200150

Table 2. nDCG@5 Scores for Different Models and Session Sizes

Fig. 1. Performance of Different Models Across Session Sizes (Risk & No Risk Combined).

5 Conclusion

We had trouble reproducing the exact results from the original paper because of limitations in the code, dataset, and computational resources. Since the 2023 code was missing, we had to use the 2024 version, but it was difficult to compare the results because the documentation didn't explain the necessary adjustments. The code was also cluttered and unfinished, making it hard and time-consuming to set up.

We were able to partially reproduce the results for the YAHOO dataset, but for the MSLR30K dataset, our results were very different from those in the paper. The ISTEELLA dataset was too large to run with the resources we had.

Using the PRIMAD Model as a framework for understanding reproducibility, the main challenges we faced were related to Data (missing or unclear dataset splits), Implementation (disorganized and incomplete code), and Platform (limited computational resources). These issues made it hard to repeat or validate the results, which are key aspects of reproducibility. While the research objective in the paper was clear, the lack of attention to practical details, like providing clear instructions or making the code portable, caused significant difficulties.

This experience shows how important it is to follow the principles of the PRIMAD Model. Improving the Implementation by organizing the code, adding better documentation, and clearly explaining dataset splits and parameter settings would make the research easier to reproduce. Additionally, ensuring the code runs well on different platforms and providing guidance on resource requirements would help make results more reliable. As discussed in the course, it's important not to trust every published result blindly and to support more efforts to improve reproducibility in research.

5.1 Code and Repository

The adapted code for this reproducibility study can be found here on github <https://github.com/M4n1us/cikm-safeultr>

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